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**Association between nitric oxide treatment and
intraventricular hemorrhage among extremely
preterm neonates in Switzerland, 2012-2020**

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Dominik Dahinden

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Publikation

Association between nitric oxide treatment and intraventricular hemorrhage among extremely preterm neonates in Switzerland, 2012-2020

Dahinden Dominik¹, Lehnick Dirk¹, Adams Mark², Joye Sebastien⁴, Natalucci Giancarlo^{2,3}, Stocker Martin^{*1,5} on behalf of the Swiss Neonatal Network

¹ Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine, University of Lucerne, Inseliwai 10, 6005 Luzern, Tel.: +41 41 229 57 50

² Newborn Research Zurich, Department of Neonatology, University Hospital of Zurich, Frauenklinikstrasse 10, 8091 Zürich, Tel.: +41 44 255 53 45

³ Family Larsson-Rosenquist Foundation Center for Neurodevelopment, Growth and Nutrition of the Newborn, Department of Neonatology, University Hospital of Zurich, Frauenklinikstrasse 10, 8091 Zürich, Tel.: +41 44 255 53 86

⁴ Department Mother-Woman-Child, Clinic of Neonatology, Lausanne University Hospital, Rue du Bugnon 46, 1005 Lausanne, Switzerland, Tel.: +41 21 314 34 64

⁵ Department of Neonatology, Children's Hospital for Central Switzerland, Spitalstrasse, 6000 Luzern 16, Tel.: +41 41 205 32 31

Corresponding author*

Prof. Dr. med. Stocker Martin

Kinderspital Luzern

Spitalstrasse

6000 Luzern 16

Tel.: +41 41 205 32 31

E-Mail: martin.stocker@luks.ch

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Abstract

Inhaled nitric oxide (iNO) treatment is routinely used to treat newborns suffering from severe respiratory distress syndrome (RDS). While the treatment is established for term born infants, its safety and efficacy remain controversial among preterm born infants. A 2017 meta-analysis focusing on this population reported a nonsignificant increase in the occurrence of severe intraventricular hemorrhage (sIVH) if infants were treated with iNO. sIVH is a dreaded complication of extreme premature birth that impairs long-term neurodevelopment. In this study, we hypothesize that iNO treatment is associated with the occurrence of sIVH among extremely preterm born infants. We investigated the Swiss population of infants born extremely preterm (< 28 weeks gestation) from 2012–2020 in a retrospective manner. The association between the treatment and sIVH was investigated by multivariable logistic regression analysis. A sensitivity analysis was performed by stratifying of the population according to the presence or absence of pulmonary hypertension of the newborn (PPHN). A total of 2101 neonates were included in the study. Among 251 patients in whom iNO treatment was applied, 62 (24.7%) suffered from sIVH, compared to 232 of the 1850 (12.5%) patients without iNO. We found no significant association between iNO treatment and the occurrence of sIVH in the presence of PPHN. It remains unclear whether the treatment is associated with the occurrence of sIVH in the absence of PPHN.

Keywords: cerebral intraventricular hemorrhage; nitric oxide; persistent fetal circulation syndrome; infant, extremely premature.

Introduction

Intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH) is a known complication of preterm birth that potentially impairs long-term neurodevelopmental outcomes.¹ Causes include bleeding in the periventricular germinal matrix, which is a highly vascularized tissue of the developing brain. This tissue starts to recede at 24 weeks gestational age (GA) until it disappears at 36-37 weeks GA. Accordingly, extremely preterm infants (born < 28 weeks gestational age) are especially vulnerable to IVH.² Stoll et al. reported that approximately 16% of this population suffers from severe intraventricular hemorrhage (sIVH).³ Cranial ultrasound investigations are used routinely to detect brain hemorrhage in preterm infants.⁴

Approximately 8% of extremely preterm born neonates suffer from persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn (PPHN).⁵ Under this condition, an increase in pulmonary arterial pressure compromises oxygenation. Underlying is a failure in the adaptation from the fetal to the newborn circulatory system hindering the postnatal reduction in pulmonary vascular resistance. If adequate oxygenation cannot be achieved, pulmonary vasodilators such as inhaled nitric oxide (iNO) may be used. Nitric oxide, formerly known as endothelium-derived relaxing factor, is an important vasodilator in pulmonary vessels. As the molecule itself is rather short-lived, administration by inhalation results in a potent and relatively selective vasodilation of ventilated lung areas. This way, oxygenation is optimized by reducing pulmonary artery pressure and ventilation/perfusion-mismatch.^{6,7}

iNO is established in term and near term born infants.⁸ However, in extremely preterm born infants however, safety and efficacy remain controversial.⁹ This may be due to differences in pathophysiological mechanisms: In extremely preterm born infants, pulmonary hypertension is more often associated with pulmonary pathologies than with failure of postnatal adaptation.¹⁰ There are also safety concerns: A meta-analysis published in 2017 reported a 20% increase in sIVH in preterm infants below 35 weeks GA when treated with iNO.⁹ However, this association did not reach statistical significance and was not restricted to extremely preterm neonates. We hypothesize that iNO treatment is associated with an increased incidence of sIVH in extremely preterm infants. To test this hypothesis, we analyzed the Swiss population of extremely preterm neonates between 2012 and 2020 in a retrospective manner.

Materials and methods

For this population-based retrospective study, the dataset used was extracted from the minimal neonatal dataset (MNDS). This registry prospectively collects data from all Swiss level III intensive care and level IIB peripheral intermediate care neonatal units, covering approximately 96% of the very preterm born population of Switzerland.¹¹ All infants born between 22 0/7 and 27 6/7 weeks GA from 01.01.2012–31.12.2020 captured in the MNDS registry were included in the analysis. As an approximation for “death before the first cranial ultrasound examination”, participants were excluded if death occurred at delivery and if no cranial ultrasound examination was documented. Furthermore, infants with unknown iNO treatment status were excluded. Data collection and evaluation for this study were approved by the Ethics Committee of the Canton of Zurich (BASEC Nr. 2022-00403). Parents were informed of the scientific use of anonymized data for research. All methods were performed in accordance with the guidelines of scientific reports for clinical trials.

Definitions

Intraventricular hemorrhage was defined as diagnosed by cranial ultrasound examination using Papile’s grades.¹² A distinction was made between intraventricular hemorrhage of any grade (anyIVH) and sIVH, defined as Papile’s grade III or IV, as the latter condition is associated with higher morbidity and mortality.¹³ All participating neonatal units performed standardized cranial ultrasound examinations within the first three days of life. Three units guaranteed an examination on the first day of life, whereas in one unit, the first cranial ultrasound examination might have taken place on the fourth day of life in certain cases. iNO treatment was defined as documented treatment with nitric oxide independent of duration and indication. The treatment was initiated at 20ppm with consecutive weaning. There was no standardized weaning protocol. Three of the nine neonatal units used iNO as emergency treatment for inadequate oxygenation independent of PPHN status. The remaining neonatal units restricted iNO treatment to neonates with a diagnosis of PPHN. PPHN was defined as a medical condition requiring specific vasodilative treatment. In the absence of information on the diagnosis of PPHN, patients were categorized as unknown for this item. Except for one neonatal unit that diagnosed PPHN according to a clinical response to iNO, all other neonatal units demanded echocardiographic evidence for the diagnosis of this condition. PPHN was only collected until the end of 2019.

Objectives

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the association between iNO treatment and sIVH. The secondary objective was to analyze the association between iNO treatment and the occurrence of anyIVH.

Statistical analyses

A retrospective cross-sectional study was performed. Statistical analyses were conducted using STATA (Version 18.0, StataCorp, College Station, Texas, USA). More than 1700 infants were expected to be included in the analysis. An incidence of 10-20% for sIVH and 10% for iNO treatment were expected. The data was summarized in a descriptive manner. Patient characteristics were compared between the iNO treatment groups using Fisher's exact test for categorical variables and the Wilcoxon rank sum test for continuous variables.

To examine the association between iNO treatment and the occurrence of IVH a non-adjusted analysis was first performed to compare the incidence of brain hemorrhage between the two treatment groups (iNO yes/no) using odds ratios with corresponding 95% confidence intervals and Fisher's exact test. As confounding variables affect the results of a retrospective comparison between two groups, the robustness of the association between iNO treatment and IVH was investigated in an adjusted analysis. Therefore, a multivariable logistic regression analysis was performed to determine odds ratios with corresponding 95% confidence intervals for the impact of iNO alone. The initial model mitigated the potential influence of all prespecified possible risk factors for the occurrence of severe intraventricular hemorrhage (full model, prespecified possible risk factors listed in Table I). Additionally, significant covariates in the model were identified by stepwise backward elimination of variables using Akaike's (AIC) and Bayesian (BIC) information criteria.

As PPHN appeared to be a significant covariate, a stratification of the population into the presence and absence of PPHN was performed. Infants with unknown PPHN status were not excluded, to ensure comparability of the results with those of other analyses. Both the non-adjusted as well as the adjusted analyses were repeated for the primary (association of iNO and sIVH) and secondary outcomes (association of iNO and anyIVH). Stepwise backward elimination of variables was not performed.

We conducted a sensitivity analysis by repeating all the analyses mentioned above with the exclusion of infants who underwent cardiac surgery or had major birth defects.

Results

During the study period, 2573 preterm infants met the inclusion criteria. After the exclusion criteria were applied, 2101 infants were included in the analysis (Figure 1). In the final dataset, there were no missing values for iNO or IVH, whereas 222 records were missing for PPHN (not captured for infants born in 2020). IVH was reported in 700 cases, of which 294 (42%) were sIVH. A total of 251 patients received iNO treatment. The infants receiving iNO treatment were significantly younger, had lower APGAR scores and more often respiratory distress (Table 1). Baseline characteristics are listed separately for the three different strata (PPHN present, PPHN absent, PPHN unknown) in the supplementary table S1 (appendix). In the group of infants with PPHN, sIVH occurred in 65 out of 283 (23%) infants, and anyIVH occurred in 142 infants (50%). iNO was applied in 180 out of 283 (64%) patients. In the absence of PPHN, sIVH occurred in 195 out of 1597 (12%) infants, and anyIVH occurred in 480 cases (30%). iNO was applied in 31 out of 1597 (2%) patients. Among the infants with unknown PPHN status, the treatment was applied in 40 out of 222 (18%) cases (Table 2).

Association between iNO treatment and IVH

In the non-adjusted analysis, iNO treatment was associated with sIVH (OR 2.29 (1.66–3.14), $p < 0.001$) and anyIVH (OR 2.80 (2.14–3.66), $p < 0.001$). This association was not detectable for sIVH after adjusting the analysis for prespecified possible risk factors for the occurrence of sIVH (OR 1.41 (0.89–2.23), $p = 0.14$). The association between iNO treatment and anyIVH was reduced but remained statistically significant after adjusting for confounding variables (OR 1.70 (1.17 - 2.48), $p = 0.005$). The results were similar after stepwise backward elimination of variables (reduced model). None of the models achieved a pseudo R² of more than 12%. Results are illustrated in Figure 2.

Association between iNO treatment and IVH stratified by PPHN

In the group of infants with a diagnosis of PPHN, there was no association between iNO treatment and sIVH detectable (non-adjusted OR 1.16 (0.65–2.07), $p = 0.63$; adjusted OR 1.02 (0.50–2.06), $p = 0.96$). In the same stratum, the association between iNO treatment and anyIVH was less pronounced but still detectable after adjusting for confounding variables (non-adjusted OR 1.71 (1.05–2.78), $p = 0.03$; adjusted OR 1.79 (1.01–3.17), $p = 0.045$). In the absence of PPHN, the odds ratios between iNO treatment and the occurrence of sIVH and anyIVH were generally greater than those in the presence of PPHN. In this group, a significant association between the treatment and the occurrence of sIVH was observed in the non-adjusted analysis. After adjusting for confounding variables, this association remained distinct but lost statistical significance (non-adjusted OR 3.03 (1.38–6.69), $p = 0.006$; adjusted OR 2.29 (0.98–5.32), $p = 0.055$). The same behavior was observed for the association of iNO treatment with the occurrence of anyIVH (non-adjusted OR 2.53

(1.24–5.16), $p = 0.011$), adjusted OR 1.80 (0.84–3.87), $p = 0.13$). The corresponding forest plots are illustrated in Figure 3.

Sensitivity analysis

Excluding infants who had undergone major cardiac surgery or had major birth defects, all the analyses mentioned above were repeated. No substantial effect on the results was observed.

Discussion

In a Swiss cohort of 2101 preterm infants less than 28 weeks GA, the hypothesized association between iNO treatment and sIVH was observed only without adjustment for confounding variables. After adjusting for confounding variables, this association could no longer be verified. The association between iNO treatment and anyIVH remained observable but was much less pronounced after adjusting for confounding variables.

These results are comparable to those of other retrospective analyses in the current literature where the association between iNO and IVH only occurred in univariate logistic regression analyses.^{14,15} Accordingly, the association between the two variables appears to be a consequence of other factors associated with both the treatment and the condition. PPHN might be one of those factors: After stepwise backward elimination of variables, the condition appeared to be a significant covariate. Therefore, we repeated the analyses after stratification of the study population according to the presence or absence of PPHN.

In the presence of PPHN, the association between iNO treatment and sIVH was no longer observable (primary outcome). For the occurrence of anyIVH, the association with iNO treatment was much less pronounced in the PPHN group. However, the association remained detectable, even after adjusting for confounding variables. A similar analysis performed by Nakanishi et al. investigated the population of the Neonatal Research Network of Japan (NRNJ) using multivariable logistic regression models: The group reported that PPHN was associated with a higher incidence of sIVH, whereas iNO treatment was not associated with in-hospital mortality or morbidity in extremely preterm born infants.¹⁶ These findings are important, as PPHN is the main indication for iNO treatment.

In the absence of PPHN, the associations between iNO treatment and the occurrence of sIVH and anyIVH appeared more pronounced than those in the non-stratified analysis. These results are comparable to those of other retrospective studies: Hsiao et al. and Carey et al. reported higher rates of in-hospital mortality if iNO was applied in the absence of PPHN. On the other hand, in both studies, the health conditions of the treatment group were worse than those of their matched control groups.^{17,18} The same bias is present in our population as well, because iNO

was used as a rescue treatment in the absence of PPHN. This might be explained by the responsiveness to iNO treatment: Boly et al. compared extremely preterm infants in terms of their response to iNO. They reported that a negative response to iNO treatment was associated with worse health outcomes.¹⁹ Ahmed et al. reported that the presence of PPHN was a strong predictor of iNO responsiveness.²⁰ Thus, in the absence of PPHN, higher rates of missing or negative responses to iNO treatment are to be expected. However, this outcome must be interpreted carefully, as iNO was applied in the absence of PPHN in only 31 cases, whereof sIVH occurred in nine cases.

Finally, we could not observe the association between iNO and sIVH, which was described in the meta-analysis performed by Barrington et al. mentioned in the introduction.⁹ The stratified analysis confirmed the missing association between the treatment and the condition in the presence of PPHN.

The strengths of our study are the large number of infants, the high geographical representation of the targeted population, and the prospective nature of data collection in the registry. Overall, our population seems to be comparable to other published cohorts regarding rates of IVH, PPHN and iNO treatment. We observed sIVH with a frequency of approximately 14% and iNO about 12%. These numbers approximately correspond to our presumptions and are comparable to the current literature.^{3,21} PPHN occurred in about 15% of cases (2012–2019). In the Japanese cohort of extremely preterm-born neonates PPHN occurred in only 8.1% of cases. This difference might underlie the more stringent diagnostic criteria of the NRNJ than of the MNDS, such as the need for sonographic evidence to diagnose PPHN.¹⁶

Study Limitations

The main limitation of the study is the retrospective nature of the analysis. The data used does not allow an analysis of the temporal relationship between iNO treatment initiation and occurrence of intraventricular hemorrhage. Infants who died in the first three days of life due to IVH might be underrepresented in our study population, as they might not have been examined by cranial ultrasound before death occurred. Infants treated with iNO could lead to performance bias due to their worse health condition. The stratification of the study population for PPHN was performed based on observations in the planned analyses, increasing the risk of confirmation bias. Finally, despite the comparability with the current literature, most circumstances of IVH were not explained by our models, as none of them achieved a pseudo R² higher than 12%.

Conclusion

Inhaled nitric oxide treatment is not associated with the occurrence of severe intraventricular hemorrhage in the presence of PPHN. It remains unclear whether the treatment itself is associated with severe intraventricular hemorrhage in the absence of PPHN.

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Author contributions

M.S. initiated, directed and funded the project. The study was designed by D.L., M.S. and D.D.. D.L. advised the team methodologically, performed all the statistical analyses, created all tables and figures and contributed to the main text. M.A. provided the dataset, advised the team scientifically and contributed to the manuscript. G.N. and S.J. advised the team neonatologically and contributed to the manuscript. D.D. wrote the main text and coordinated the exchange between the coauthors as a doctoral student and the lead author of the study.

Data availability statement

Additional data are available by emailing the SwissNeoNet coordinator at mark.adams@usz.ch

Additional information

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Tables

Table I. Summary table by treatment group (iNO)

	nitric oxide treatment		total n = 2'101	p-value
	no n = 1850	yes n = 251		
Prespecified risk factors				
Gestational age (weeks)	26 (25; 27)	25 (24; 26)	26 (25; 27)	<.001
Birth weight (grams)	800 (660; 950)	730 (610; 860)	790 (655; 950)	<.001
Sex				0.030
<i>female</i>	882 (48%)	102 (41%)	984 (47%)	
<i>male</i>	967 (52%)	148 (59%)	1115 (53%)	
<i>unknown / non-determinable</i>	1 (.05%)	1 (.4%)	2 (.1%)	
Prenatal steroids				0.062
<i>no</i>	137 (7%)	23 (9%)	160 (8%)	
<i>unknown</i>	9 (.5%)	1 (.4%)	10 (.5%)	
<i>incomplete</i>	415 (22%)	39 (16%)	454 (22%)	
<i>complete</i>	1289 (70%)	188 (75%)	1477 (70%)	
5 min APGAR Score	7 (5; 8)	6 (4; 7)	7 (5; 8)	<.001
Respiratory distress				0.066
<i>none</i>	35 (2%)	1 (.4%)	36 (2%)	
<i>meconium aspiration syndrome</i>	2 (.1%)	1 (.4%)	3 (.1%)	
<i>infectious pneumopathy</i>	8 (.4%)	5 (2%)	13 (.6%)	
<i>other or unknown causes</i>	1805 (98%)	244 (97%)	2049 (98%)	
Patent ductus arteriosus (PDA)				0.005
<i>absent</i>	898 (49%)	98 (39%)	996 (47%)	
<i>present</i>	952 (51%)	153 (61%)	1105 (53%)	
Surfactant admission				<.001
<i>not given</i>	352 (19%)	11 (4%)	363 (17%)	
<i>given</i>	1498 (81%)	240 (96%)	1738 (83%)	
Persistent pulmonary hypertension (PPHN)				<.001
<i>absent</i>	1565 (85%)	31 (12%)	1596 (76%)	
<i>present</i>	103 (6%)	180 (72%)	283 (13%)	
<i>unknown (not captured in year 2020)</i>	182 (10%)	40 (16%)	222 (11%)	
Sepsis				<.001
<i>absent</i>	942 (51%)	80 (32%)	1022 (49%)	
<i>culture-negative</i>	484 (26%)	87 (35%)	571 (27%)	
<i>proven</i>	424 (23%)	84 (33%)	508 (24%)	

Median (Q1; Q3) and Wilcoxon rank-sum test for continuous variables.

n (%) and Fisher's exact test for categorical variables.

Table 2a. Frequencies of patients (n(%)) with severe intraventricular hemorrhage (sIVH) by treatment group (iNO)

Presence of sIVH	iNO treatment		Total
	no	Yes	
Non-stratified analysis	(n = 2,101)		
no	1,618 (87.5%)	189 (75.3%)	1,807 (86.0%)
yes	232 (12.5%)	62 (24.7%)	294 (14.0%)
PPHN present	(n = 283)		
no	81 (78.6%)	137 (76.1%)	218 (77.0%)
yes	22 (21.4%)	43 (23.9%)	65 (23.0%)
PPHN absent	(n = 1,596)		
no	1,379 (88.1%)	22 (71.0%)	1,401 (87.8%)
yes	186 (11.9%)	9 (29.0%)	195 (12.2%)
PPHN unknown	(n = 222)		
no	158 (86.8%)	30 (75.0%)	188 (84.7%)
yes	24 (13.2%)	10 (25.0%)	34 (15.3%)

Table 2b. Frequencies of patients (n(%)) with intraventricular hemorrhage of any grade (anyIVH) by treatment group (iNO)

Presence of anyIVH	iNO treatment		Total
	no	yes	
non-stratified analysis	(n = 2,101)		
no	1,288 (69.6%)	113 (45.0%)	1,401 (66.7%)
yes	562 (30.4%)	138 (55.0%)	700 (33.3%)
PPHN present	(n = 283)		
no	60 (58.3%)	81 (45.0%)	141 (49.8%)
yes	43 (41.7%)	99 (55.0%)	142 (50.2%)
PPHN absent	(n = 1,596)		
no	1,101 (70.4%)	15 (48.4%)	1,116 (69.9%)
yes	464 (29.6%)	16 (51.6%)	480 (30.1%)
PPHN unknown	(n = 222)		
no	127 (69.8%)	17 (42.5%)	144 (64.9%)
yes	55 (30.2%)	23 (57.5%)	78 (35.1%)

Figures

Figure 1. Population selection flowchart

MNDS: minimal neonatal dataset. iNO: inhaled nitric oxide. PPHN: persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn.

Figure 2. Association between iNO treatment and intraventricular hemorrhage, non-stratified analysis

CI: confidence interval. iNO: inhaled nitric oxide treatment. IVH: intraventricular hemorrhage.

Figure 3. Association between nitric oxide treatment and intraventricular hemorrhage stratified by PPHN

CI: confidence interval. PPHN: persistent hypertension of the newborn. iNO: inhaled nitric oxide treatment. IVH: intraventricular hemorrhage. Population size: non-stratified ($n = 2,101$), PPHN present ($n = 283$), PPHN absent ($n = 1,596$), PPHN unknown ($n = 222$).

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Curriculum Vitae

Dominik Dahinden

16.06.1997	Geboren in Luzern
2002 - 2008	Primarschule in Würzenbach, Luzern
2008 - 2014	Kantonsschule Alpenquai, Luzern
2015 - 2016	Biologiestudium an der Universität Basel
2016 - 2023	Medizinstudium an den Universitäten Zürich und Luzern
10/2023	Eidg. Examen Humanmedizin an der Universität Zürich
11/2023 - 06/2025	Assistenzarzt Allgemeine Innere Medizin, Spital Nidwalden
Seit 07/2025	Praxisassistent, Lumenpraxis Schenkon